

MORPHOFUNCTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MONBELYARD CATTLE IN THE CONDITIONS OF KARAKALPAKSTAN

J.T. Ilyasova¹, Sh. K. Amirov²

PhD student, Karakalpakstan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnologies¹

PhD on Agricultural Sciences, Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of Agroinnovations and
Research²

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14993580>

Abstract. *The study provides information on cows imported from France and their characteristics after importation. It examines the morphofunctional properties of the udders of cows imported to Karakalpakstan during different seasons. The study found that cows in the experimental group (Group II) had superior udder measurements compared to the control group (Group I), specifically in udder circumference, length, and width. These measurements exceeded those of the control group by 2.5 cm ($P < 0.01$), 1.4 cm ($P < 0.05$), and 2 cm ($P < 0.01$), respectively. A similar trend was observed in udder depth, where the front and rear depths were higher by 2 cm and 1.7 cm, respectively ($P < 0.05$). An analysis of the functional properties of the udders revealed that cows in the experimental group had a higher milk flow rate, recorded at 0.17 kg/min ($P < 0.05$). At the conclusion of the study, the authors determined that the morphofunctional characteristics of the udders of Montbéliarde cows imported from France met all the required standards in the classification process. They concluded that the selection of cows based on udder characteristics by French breeding scientists not only improved udder traits but also had a positive impact on milk productivity.*

Keywords: *monbelyard, breed, dairy cattle, cow, mammary gland, lactation, udder, morphological indicators, functional characteristics, teat, bowl-shaped, basin-shaped, teat length, milk yield rate, udder index, udder circumference, udder width, etc.*

Introduction

It is known that factors such as heredity, breed characteristics, nutrition, housing conditions, age, live weight, and milking techniques and technologies affect the milk yield of cows. While these factors are important, the mammary glands in the udder and their activity remain one of the most significant influences on milk production. In industrial technology, cows must be suitable for machine milking to ensure efficient milk production.

The rapid and effective improvement of dairy cattle herds and the formation of animals that meet the demands of mechanized farms cannot be imagined without evaluating their technological qualities. The morphofunctional characteristics of the mammary glands determine the milk yield and lactation of the cows.

The suitability of cows for machine milking is primarily characterized by the duration of milking and the uniformity of milk extraction from the four compartments of the udder. High-yielding cows typically have a udder shape that is basin-like or cup-like, characterized by well-developed teats.

Cows that are suitable for machine milking typically have udders that are large, of medium size, and well-attached to the body, with teats of equal length and thickness. If the four compartments of the udder are equally developed, there is no need to massage the udder at the end of milking. Many researchers believe that the shape of the udder is an important indicator in cow selection, as there is a positive correlation between udder shape and milk productivity. By selecting cows based on the morphological characteristics of their udders, it is also possible to improve the functional properties of the udder.

In practice, the functional properties of the udder are considered significant indicators, with attention given to the speed and duration of milking. These indicators are genetically based traits. The rate of milk production is closely linked to various factors, including milk yield, the stability coefficient of lactation, lactation duration, and mastitis resistance.

The mammary gland of a cow determines its milk productivity. It is known that to produce one liter of milk, approximately 400-500 liters of blood must flow through the udder. This leads to the conclusion that the udder has a very high number of blood vessels. For instance, if a cow yields 20 liters of milk per day, about 8-10 tons of blood must pass through the udder.

The production of milk in the udder involves not only the mammary glands but also the entire organism, systems, and tissues. Therefore, milk production is a complex process. The mammary gland undergoes various changes during lactation, with its functional activity varying at different levels. In contrast, other glands remain consistently active throughout. This means that during lactation, cells in the mammary gland undergo processes of degradation and renewal. At the end of lactation, the glandular tissue in the mammary glands decreases, while during the final stages, the degraded gland cells rapidly regenerate, ensuring an increase in milk productivity.

The length, width, and depth of the udder express its shape. In cows, udder shapes can be basin-like, round, or goat-like. Among these, basin-shaped and cup-shaped udders are considered superior, as cows with such udders are distinguished by high productivity. These udder shapes are well-suited for machine milking and also exhibit a high milk flow rate. They are resistant to mastitis, as their quarters are equally developed, and dry milking periods are not observed. Cup-shaped udders are characterized by a moderately oval shape with average length and width, and they are described as being deeper.

The shape of the udder in cows is a hereditary trait. Therefore, in selection work, the mother of the chosen bulls should ideally have a basin-shaped or cup-shaped udder. Such udder shapes are well-suited for industrial milk production. This trait positively affects the cost of milk production, serving as one of the factors that contribute to the economic efficiency of the farm. Cows with these udder shapes require less time for milking due to their high milk yield characteristics.

Aim of the Research

The aim of the study is to investigate, analyze, and draw conclusions about the morphofunctional characteristics of the udder in mature Monbelyard cattle.

Object of the Research and Methods Used

The research was conducted on Monbelyard cattle raised at the "Qung'irotbody Mexri" farm in the Kerder village of Nukus district. The morphological indicators of the udder were studied during the third month of lactation, specifically 30 to 60 minutes before milking. The following measurements were taken: udder circumference, length and width of the udder, depth of the front and rear quarters, and length of the teats, using a measuring tape.

The functional characteristics of the udder were evaluated through control milking, during which the daily milk yield and the time spent on milking were recorded. The obtained numerical data were processed biometrically using the method proposed by N.A. Ploxinskiy.

Research Results and Analysis

In foreign countries, breeders have long considered udder shape in their selection and sorting practices. In France, similar measures have been implemented, leading to positive results. Taking these observations into account, we aimed to study the morphofunctional characteristics of the udders of Monbelyard cattle imported from France to the Republic of Karakalpakstan during various seasons.

In our research, we conducted two lactations for the heifers imported from France after their arrival on the farm. It is known that by the third lactation, cows reach maturity. Therefore, we decided to study the morphological and functional characteristics of the udders of cows in their third calving age.

Currently, several udder shapes corresponding to the breed can be observed in cows. In beef-dairy breeds, cup-shaped udders are more common, while in dairy breeds, basin-shaped udders are frequently encountered. We visually assessed the shape of the udders in the cows. The obtained results are presented in the following table.

Table 1

Distribution of Udder Shapes Among the Experimental Groups of Cows

Groups	number	udder shapes			
		cup-shaped		basin-shaped	
		number	%	number	%
I (control)	15	10	66,7	5	33,3
II (experiment)	15	9	60,0	6	40,0

Analysis of Udder Shapes in the Experimental Groups

From the data in Table 1, it is evident that in Group I, cows with cup-shaped udders constitute 67.6%, while those with basin-shaped udders make up 33.3%. There was little difference when compared to Group II, where this indicator accounted for only 6.7%.

The udders of Monbelyard cattle are predominantly cup-shaped, and the presence of basin-shaped udders confirms that breeders have taken measures concerning this trait. Neither round nor goat-shaped udders were observed in either group, as such shapes are generally less suitable for machine milking.

When assessing the suitability of cows for machine milking, the morphological characteristics of the udder play a crucial role. To evaluate these characteristics, it is necessary to take measurements of the udder.

Taking these points into account, we measured the udder dimensions of Monbelyard cattle imported during various seasons in our experiments during the third month of lactation, specifically 0.5 to 1.0 hours before milking, and conducted the appropriate analyses.

In addition, the functional characteristics of the udder were also studied to determine the suitability of cows for machine milking.

For this purpose, in our research, we measured the daily milk yield and the time spent milking, and based on these indicators, we examined the milk production rate of the cows. The obtained data are presented in the following table.

Table 2

"Morfofunctional indicators of the udder of cows in the experimental groups, cm"

Indicators	groups (n=15)			
	I (control)		II (experiment)	
	$\bar{X} \pm S\bar{x}$	Sv, %	$\bar{X} \pm S\bar{x}$	Sv, %
udder circumference	114,3±0,49	1,67	116,8±0,44**	1,45
udder length	33,7±0,37	4,30	35,1±0,41*	4,50
Udder width	23,9±0,27	4,44	25,9±0,41**	6,18
anterior udder depth	24,3±0,35	5,53	26,3±0,33**	4,87
posterior udder depth	26,1±0,34	5,12	27,8±0,26***	3,65
length of the anterior teats	7,61±0,11	5,41	8,05±0,12*	5,93
length of the posterior teats	7,02±0,08	4,38	7,39±0,10*	5,16
functional characteristics				
average daily milk yield, kg	13,10±0,34	9,96	14,89±0,52*	13,63
milking duration, minutes	10,79±0,25	9,08	10,83±0,36	12,93
milk yield rate, kg/minute	1,22±0,04	11,92	1,39±0,06*	16,47
Udder index %	42,8±0,26	2,38	43,1±0,15	1,35

Notice: *P<0,05, **P<0,01, ***P<0,001

The table data indicates that the cows in group II had superior udder circumference, length, and width measurements compared to the cows in group I (control), with differences of 2.5 cm (P<0.01), 1.4 cm (P<0.05), and 2 cm (P<0.01), respectively. This trend was also observed in the depth measurements, where the front and rear depths were significantly higher by 2 cm and 1.7 cm (P<0.05). We witnessed that these measurements reflected in the milk productivity indicators of the cows in subsequent experiments.

The length of the front and rear teats of the cows in group II was longer by 0.44 cm and 0.37 cm, respectively, compared to group I (P<0.05). Other measurements also showed a significant advantage for the cows in group II.

In our experiments, we studied the functional characteristics of the udder to provide a more comprehensive assessment. For this purpose, control milkings were conducted on cows in both the experimental and control groups using a special milking machine. The amount of milk collected from the cows and the time spent were determined, allowing us to evaluate the milk yield rate of the cows.

The data from the table shows that the average daily milking difference between the groups was 1.79 kg (P<0.05). As noted above, the larger udder measurements in the experimental group positively influenced this indicator. The milking time for cows in the experimental group was extended by 0.04 minutes compared to the control group, which can be explained by the increased milk yield. Focusing on the milk yield rate, the cows in the experimental group had a higher rate of 0.17 kg/minute (P<0.05).

Another indicator that reflects the cows' adaptation to machine milking is the udder index. The data indicates a slight advantage in the udder index for the experimental group (0.3%). Nevertheless, we observed that the morpho-functional characteristics of the udders of the Montbeliard breed cows imported from France fully met the required standards.

Conclusions

The cows in group II exhibited superior udder circumference, length, and width measurements compared to the cows in group I (control), with respective advantages of 2.5 cm ($P<0.01$), 1.4 cm ($P<0.05$), and 2 cm ($P<0.01$). This trend was also reflected in the depth measurements, where the front and rear depths were significantly higher by 2 cm and 1.7 cm ($P<0.05$).

When studying the functional characteristics of the cows' udders, the experimental group recorded a higher milk yield rate of 0.17 kg/minute ($P<0.05$).

It can be stated that the morpho-functional characteristics of the udders of Montbeliard breed cows imported from France met all the requirements set during the evaluation. The presence of basin-shaped udders in this breed indicates that French breeding scientists paid attention to the relevant characteristics during selection and breeding processes.

REFERENCES

1. Дунин И.М. Совершенствование скота черно-пестрой породы в Среднем Поволжье. М.2018, С.279
2. Ковтоногов М.В. Влияние голштинизации черно-пестрых коров на морфофункциональные показатели вымени коров в ОАО “Заря” Хабаровского края. 2019, №3. С.4-6.
3. Хайсанов Д.П. Использование голштинской породы в молочном скотоводстве Поволжья. Ульяновск. 2017, С. 307
4. Велиток И.Г. Технология машинного доения коров. М.Колос. 1995.С.256
5. Бондарь Р.М. Размер, форма вымени и состав, скорость молокоотдачи как признаки отбора коров. Дисс.канд.с.х.наук. Белая Церковь. 1998, С.137
6. Гаркавый Ф.Л. Селекция коров и машинное доение. Колос. 2000, С.158
7. Плохинский Н.А. Руководство по биометрии для зоотехников. М: Колос, 1969.С.256
8. Анисимова Е. Морфофункциональные свойства вымени симментальских коров разных типов. Научно-производственные разработки и рекомендации. 2015.С.36-37
9. Tsuchievna, A. M., Kuzibaevich, A. S., Kurbanova, S. E., Abdurafievich, M. K., & Tajievich, G. S. (2022). The use of technological measures in improving the body growth and morphofunctional properties of the udder of cows. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 8-15.